

Degree in International Relations
University of A Coruña

Year 2024/2025
Sociology of Globalization

The Sephora Kids Dilemma: a global phenomenon.

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Abstract

The Sephora Kids phenomenon exemplifies an expanding international trend in which pre-teens, swayed by social media and a culture of consumerism, interact with beauty and skincare products aimed at adults. This study investigates the convergence of consumerism, social media, and teenager's mental health to comprehend how beauty ideals perpetuated through online platforms influence the self-perception and behavior of young individuals. Through a mixed-methods approach to gathering data—both qualitative and quantitative—this study investigates the role of influencers, the impact of marketing strategies targeting minors, and parental complicity in fostering this trend, with an especial focus on the influence of Family Vlogging. Data was collected through online surveys, digital ethnography, participant observations, and secondary analyses of retail worker testimonials. These findings highlight the normalization of unrealistic standards of beauty, which exacerbate mental health problems like body dissatisfaction and anxiety, particularly among vulnerable age groups such as the protagonists of the study. This research also examines the ethical implications of corporate marketing strategies and family vlogging trends that encourage early exposure to beauty products. The results show significant gaps in parental control, the growing influence of social media on consumer behavior, and the potential long-term consequences for society. Through the exploration of these key issues, the study contributes to the broader discussion on globalization, digital culture, and the mental health of adolescents. Future research should investigate how these practices impact individuals in the long term and what cultural nuances shape beauty standards worldwide.

Keywords: Sephora Kids, social media, consumerism, mental health, beauty standards, globalization, adolescents, trend, makeup, TikTok, Instagram.

1. Introduction

The Sephora Kids refers to a phenomenon of young individuals, typically girls aged 8 to 15, who are obsessed with skincare and makeup. This group, often classified as pre-teens or "tweens," has become increasingly prominent on social media. According to Dr. Lauren Prenzi, a New York-based dermatologist, these young consumers exhibit a growing curiosity for products such as creams, facial masks, and facial peels, many of which are formulated for more mature skin types. The phenomenon gained attention primarily through these young consumers frequenting makeup stores, particularly Sephora, where they engage in disruptive behavior. They often damage display products and testers from luxury skincare brands like Drunk Elephant, Glow Recipe, Sol de Janeiro, and Laneige. A common trend among **Sephora Kids** is their attraction to colorful, interactive packaging that mirrors the visual aesthetics of popular beauty influencers on platforms like TikTok. Influenced by beauty gurus, these tweens sometimes engage in what they call "*skincare smoothies*," a practice where they mix multiple skincare products together, often leading to the destruction of testers in stores. This behavior, combined with their often bratty and entitled attitudes, has sparked online discussion among netizens, who criticize the phenomenon for its consumerist tendencies and lack of respect for the value of beauty products.

In this research paper we will explore this global phenomenon and its possible implications on mental health; to have a broader understanding of the research questions and their importance, we will firstly define the key sub concepts that will be touched in the research project, following Cambridge Dictionary and Urban Dictionary definitions.

- **Social media:** websites and computer programs that allow people to communicate and share information, opinions, pictures, videos etc. on the internet, especially social networking websites. E.g. TikTok, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter).
- **Consumerism:** the situation in which too much affection is given to buying and owning things.
- **Trend:** a new development in clothing, make-up, etc.
 - **Micro trend:** a short-lived trend influenced by social media.

- **Family vlogging:** refers to the practice of parents or caregivers sharing their family's daily life, activities, and experiences on video-sharing platforms (normally YouTube).

2. Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the influence of social media on the mental health of adolescents, particularly in the context of the beauty standards as ongoing micro trends in a capitalistic society. We ought to explore the interconnectivity of this phenomena with globalization as well as the socioeconomical aspect of this phenomenon. Understanding that this has its origin in the consumerism that has been prevalent and increasing over the years. The following research questions have been developed to explore the key areas of interest in this domain.

How does consumerism manifest in the beauty industry, particularly through social media influencers and platforms like TikTok?

This question aims to understand the mechanisms behind consumerism, focusing on how capitalism and influencers drive consumer behavior and the desire for products tied to social acceptance and self-image enhancement. For this we will also explore the following Internet dynamics such as the hashtags: #haul, #hugehaul, #aesthetic and the range of age at the use of TikTok.

Where does the need for makeup in the Sephora Kids come from? Why do parents allow this?

It explores the origin of the desire for makeup among young people, particularly in relation to Sephora Kids, and examines why parents permit such behaviors, potentially influenced by societal beauty standards and pressures as well as the phenomenon of Family Vlogging and its negative aspects. This question will also explore the dermatological impact on the kid's faces. Research on adolescent development can provide a foundation for understanding these dynamics.

Why does the obsession with beauty standards and social acceptance negatively affect mental health, and how do radical physical changes impact individuals psychologically?

This investigates how unattainable beauty standards impact kid's and teen's mental health (e.g., cosmetic and surgical procedures), and the need for social acceptance. It seeks to understand the psychological aspect and mechanisms behind body image concerns and the effect of social comparison. To expand our knowledge on this we will use psychological theories (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2015; Tiggemann & Slater, 2013) and for, again, popular hashtags that could answer this need already existent but expanded in the social media frame: #glowup, #grwm, #skincare.

In the future, could it get worse? How would society be affected if it worsens?

This concluding question looks at the potential long-term effects of the current beauty trend and consumer culture. It speculates on whether the pressure to conform will worsen and how this could negatively impact society, particularly in terms of mental health and social dynamics.

3. Literature Review

The intersection of **social media**, **consumerism**, and **mental health** has become a critical area of study in recent years, especially concerning adolescents. This literature review examines three key themes within the field: (1) the role of social media in shaping adolescent consumer behavior, (consumerism), (2) the internalization of beauty standards, and (3) the psychological and mental health implications of these phenomena. While existing research offers a valuable insight, significant gaps remain, due to the lack of studies concerning the Sephora Kids phenomena (also because its recent origin, 2023) and regarding the long-term consequences and cultural nuances of these trends.

1) Social media and adolescent consumer behavior.

Social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube have shaped how teens engage with consumer culture. Studies highlight how platforms leverage algorithms to

promote personalized content that aligns with users' interests, including beauty and lifestyle trends. For instance, Kuss and Griffiths (2017) argue that these platforms normalize beauty ideals and subtly encourage teens to adopt consumption behaviors tied to those. Similarly, research on "haul videos" demonstrates how influencers drive purchasing force by showcasing products, fostering a sense of aspiration among young viewers (IAB Spain, 2022).

The concept of "authenticity" on TikTok plays a pivotal role in how beauty and trends are perceived by adolescents. A study on TikTok's algorithm by The Atlantic (2021) highlights how the platform creates a feedback loop, delivering hyper-personalized content that feels relatable yet aspirational. This dynamic is further complicated when teens tend to associate material goods, such as beauty products, with social status and self-worth (Erizal, 2021). As we are analyzing kids, this influence is on especially vulnerable people due to their developmental stage and reliance on peer validation. This Sephora Kids are drawn into beauty and the cosmetic culture, mimicking the habits and mannerisms of older influencers (Lobato, 2023).

Consumerism is a word that was born around the 1920s and constitutes one of the fundamental pillars of our society, known as the "*consumer society*" (Bauman, 2007). This phenomenon developed especially in the second half of the 20th century due to a combination of factors such as industrialization and the growth of mass production, which made it possible to manufacture large quantities of goods at an increasingly lower unit cost; a favorable political and institutional environment, driven by the strengthening of the welfare state; increased business competitiveness; and the expansion of advertising.

From the 1950s onwards, consumption became "massified": luxury was democratized and access to "secondary" consumption (i.e., that which is not strictly necessary for survival) was expanded, even for large sectors of the population that previously spent most of their resources on basic needs such as food or electricity. Consumerism, as we know it today, has come to include spaces that were not traditionally associated with shopping, such as museums

and universities, where we find university clothing stores, bookstores with jewelry, rugs and decorative items, as well as restaurants and coffee shops.

Therefore, consumerism is not only related to unbridled buying and waste, but also to the spaces where we spend our free time, the way we build and transform our relationships with others, our relationship with art and culture, or the way we forge our identity.

The consumer world is a constantly evolving universe, shaped by social, technological and economic changes. Each year brings with it new trends and perspectives that influence both people's purchasing decisions and companies' strategies.

Today, social networks have become one of the most widely used tools, especially by teenagers, as they allow them to interact and communicate interactively thanks to web-based technologies. Among the most popular platforms are blogs, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and, currently, TikTok, which has set a significant trend. During the pandemic, the use of TikTok grew significantly. People are not only consuming videos, but also using the platform to express their creativity and uniqueness by creating audiovisual content.

Social media and consumerism are closely linked, as these platforms have a significant impact on consumer behavior. Bauman argues that consumerism is not only about acquiring goods but also defining one's identity through consumption. Through attractive visual content, targeted promotions and direct interaction with users, social networks create an environment that constantly stimulates the desire to purchase products or services.

A clear example is the use of influencers and content creators, who through posts, videos and stories promote brands and products. This type of advertising, which appears more authentic compared to traditional advertising, generates greater trust in users and leads them to consider purchases as spontaneous decisions. In addition, advanced algorithms personalize content, displaying products tailored to users' individual preferences, which increases the likelihood of purchase.

Since its launch in 2017, TikTok has become one of the fastest growing apps globally, and its number of users continues to increase massively year after year. This is the number of monthly active users since 2017, and as we can see, it has grown dramatically.

Another interesting fact is the age ranges of users: as we can see, 63% of TikTok users are between 10 and 29 years old, and it is estimated that 35% of TikTok's user base in the United States belongs to Generation Z.

Based on this we understand that this shift from necessity-based consumption to identity-driven consumption has transformed how people, particularly adolescents, interact with their environment and self-image. In a society where self-worth is increasingly tied to consumer goods, social media platforms, such as TikTok, amplify these pressures by promoting unattainable beauty ideals. If we join this to the psychological vulnerable state of teens, who suffer from the need of self-acceptance (a theme that we will discuss later in our research) enterprises have the best crop field to sell to these children, solutions to their insecurities when they don't even know how to count decimals. This is particularly evident in the Sephora Kids phenomenon, where young girls feel the need to purchase a use makeup at an extremely early age.

Social media dynamics, such as the rise of hashtags like **#haul** (according to Cambridge Dictionary, "all the things someone buys on an occasion when they go shopping"), **#grwm** (Get Ready with Me; in which beauty gurus or girls show their skincare and makeup routine, normally consisting of a lot of steps) and **#aesthetic**. These trends do not only encourage the purchase of an exaggerated quantity of physical products, but also establish a collective identity around consumption. Adolescents, especially those within Generation Z and Alpha, are particularly vulnerable influences due to the pervasive nature of social media in their daily lives.

2) Internalization of Western Beauty Standards.

The normalization of beauty ideals on social media has led to the internalization of unattainable standards. Research by Mueller et al. (2023) finds that young women exposed

to appearance-focused TikTok are more likely to experience body dissatisfaction and engage in harmful weight-loss behaviors. Studies by Fardouly & Vartanian (2015) and Tiggeman & Slater (2013) explore the influence of media exposure on body dissatisfaction on young women, supporting these ideas. Similarly, Tiggeman & Slater (2013) argue that social media's portrayal of "ideal" body types can result in self-objectification and negative body image, especially those teenage girls engaged with the appearance-focused content.

These authors conclude that an over exposure to highly curated images of influencers, celebrities and peers can have a horrible impact in their mental health with the result of high levels of depression and anxiety. Other studies reveal that the internalization of beauty standards is strongest when appearance ideals are promoted by similar peers, creating a vicious cycle of comparison and self-criticism (Mueller et al., 2023). This is consistent with findings from Vanity Fair Italia (2023), which discuss the social pressures adolescents face to conform and the resulting impacts on their self-esteem and body image.

While studies like these provide valuable insights into short-term effects, they remain having a significant gap in longitudinal research exploring the long-term psychological effects of sustained exposure to social media beauty standards on adolescents' mental health, something that this research project will try to explore and explain their origin and possible future.

Until recently, makeup use in minors was less common, typically beginning around age 16 or 17. Society valued natural beauty, with varied and unique facial features. However, today's beauty standards often focus on modified, androgynous looks that blur ethnic identities. Parents may allow their children to wear makeup for fun or self-expression, not fully considering the psychological risks associated with these trends.

The real concern is how this growing trend impacts mental health, particularly through a condition known as "*cosmeticorexia*," individuals become obsessed with their appearance due to excessive use of cosmetics. This can't be classified as a disorder but has helped dermatologists to put a name on this condition (Lobato, 2023). Social media exacerbates this issue by promoting beauty ideals that are unattainable, leading to anxiety and low self-

esteem, especially among young children who compare themselves to influencers and celebrities.

3) Mental Health Implications

The psychological consequences of social media engagement with beauty content are alarming. Several studies link excessive use of TikTok to increased rates of anxiety, depression, and body dissatisfaction among adolescents (PMC, 2023) as we have previously mentioned. For example, targeted exposure to appearance-related content has been shown to amplify eating disorder symptoms, particularly among users already vulnerable to body image concerns (Mueller et al., 2023). This aligns with findings from EMBOPress (2023), which demonstrate the role of social media in perpetuating pro-ana and pro-mia content, (pro anorexia, and pro bulimia content, normally disguised as “toxic motivation” or with a whole language used in the community to pass the algorithm’s banning system).

Furthermore, the rise of the Sephora Kids has introduced new challenges. Lobato (2023) warns that these attitudes undermine the development of healthy self-esteem and body image, fostering a constant sense of inadequacy. This pressure to conform to these trends often leads to eating disorders, such as anorexia and bulimia, as children feel the need to alter their bodies to achieve these ideals. This shift has contributed to a significant rise in eating disorders. While prior to the expansion of social media, the global prevalence of eating disorders was around 1-3%, by 2020, reports showed a 16% increase, especially among adolescents and young adults. Social media, along with time spent at home during the pandemic, amplified body image concerns, leading to a 60% increase in eating disorder treatment requests.

Another important aspect to note about these kids is the education they are receiving, as well the effects that social media it’s having on their brains and their attention span. Internet addiction, particularly among Generation Alpha (those born between the beginning of 2013 until the mid 2020s), is increasingly linked to behavioral challenges and issues such as outbursts, and rude interactions in public spaces like stores. Studies suggest that prolonged exposure to short-form content (30 seconds or less) such as TikTok and YouTube Shorts promotes dopamine addiction, lowering attention spans and impairing emotional regulation

(Yang et al., 2022). These effects can exacerbate children's attention when their expectations, shaped by the instant gratification of digital media, are not met.

Research shows that children and teenagers with internet addiction often experience significant difficulties in emotion regulation and social cognition. This results in increased impulsivity, difficulty interpreting social cues, and challenges in managing interpersonal interactions (Saatçioğlu et al., 2023). As observed in some minors, like the ones recorded in social media under the hashtag #SephoraKids, the pressure to conform to these standards can result in frustration or aggressive behavior as seen in the videos online, when confronted with real-world limitations (Berryman et al., 2018). Digital interactions, rapid and artificial, condition children to seek constant validation and immediate satisfaction instead of dopamine that could be found in things at normal pace, such as drawing, playing with toys...

While the literature establishes strong links between social media use and mental health challenges, less attention has been paid to the role of parental oversight and cultural differences in shaping these outcomes. Little is known about the motivations of parents who allow their children to participate into these attitudes. This research project will try to navigate in the conclusions the valuable insights that could be provided by briefly analyzing other directly related phenomena such as the Family Vlogging.

Already defined, Family Vlogging can serve as a trampoline to seek social approval through platforms, where trends related to self-image are prevalent. This desire for validation is a key factor driving teens and, particularly in this case, kids to engage in these trends as social media provides immediate feedback through likes and shares, reinforcing the notion that self-worth is tied to appearance and consumption (Fardouly & Vartanian, 2015; Tiggemann & Slater, 2013). Moreover, studies show that this need for social approval can be exacerbated by the visibility of social media.

Family Vlogging serves its purpose as parents may see the exposure of their children to online platforms to gain social capital and financial rewards. This can make parents more inclined to allow their children to participate in trends even if they have long-term negative effects,

or turning them into Sephora Kids, as they perceive benefit through the controversy that generates into likes, shares, comments and mainly money (Archer & Delmo, 2023). One popular case that illustrates the problems and negative effects of Family Vlogging is the 8 Passengers Case. Family Vlogging at a first glance can look like something entirely positive but it underscores its dark side: parents willing to expose their children, even if they cannot understand the long-term effects of their exposure on the Internet, for financial gains. The welfare of children takes a second place, emotional and psychological risks are involved, including how being constantly filmed can affect a child's development, sense of privacy, and mental well-being (Archer & Delmo, 2023). This research project will explore this aspect and its consequences in the Conclusion Section.

Other gap in the literature review is the neglect of the cultural variations on beauty standards and how with the growing globalization and social media trends these are generalized and manifested globally. Trend by trend social and physical differences between individuals are erased to establish the "new makeup micro trend" which have as a result the homogenization of the extremely changing beauty standard. Chae (2017) adds that "*the algorithms of social media platforms tend to prioritize content that adheres to popular beauty standards, reinforcing a uniform image of what is considered beautiful*" (p. 9). As a result, users may internalize these beauty ideals, leading to "*greater conformity to homogenized beauty standards*" (p. 10), this applied to kids ranging from 8 to 15 is extremely dangerous and could lead to further mental health issues now and in their future.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Procedure and Instruments.

For this research project we will use a mixed approach: both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Due to the qualitative nature of the topic, we'll try to answer and understand to formulate our results considering this.

1. **Interviews:** Our primary qualitative approach will involve conducting structured and semi-structured interviews with employees from Sephora and various other makeup stores to comment on distinctions and patterns between these environments. While interviewing the

Sephora "kids" (minors, ranging from 8 to 13 years old, who represent the study's focal subjects) may present ethical and practical challenges, we will prioritize gathering detailed testimonies from employees who interact directly with them to gain insights into their behaviors, motivations, and impact on store dynamics.

2. **Visual Methods:** Given the media-centric nature of this phenomenon, we will utilize digital ethnography through social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, X (formerly Twitter), and YouTube. This approach will enable us to collect and analyze content relevant to Sephora "kids," examining trends, public discourse, and representations that shape their identity and influence. These visual resources are the parents' uploaded videos, and ones that are on the hashtags #familyvlogging, #sephora, #haul, #grwm and several other related ones. We will also use essay commentary videos from YouTube that have produced different perspectives and engaged in the origin of the phenomenon and its controversy. On the other hand, opinions of netizens on X or art related to the matter.

3. **Participant Observation/Participator Methods:** To deepen our understanding of the experiences and social interactions of makeup store employees, we will engage in participant observation. By immersing ourselves in their day-to-day roles (from 6PM to 8PM because these are the range of hours in which the Sephora Kids are the most active, due to their school schedule), we aim to gain firsthand insights into the operational dynamics, customer interactions, and cultural contexts that characterize their workplace, with particular attention to phenomena surrounding the Sephora "kids." In this method it is crucial to understand that, due to the ethical technicalities of observing children we will not record or take images, we will simply watch the overall ambience and atmosphere in the store.

4. **Surveys:** In addition to the qualitative methods, we will incorporate a quantitative component through surveys. The surveys will be distributed among a broad range of makeup store employees and customers to gather data on their perceptions, experiences, and attitudes toward the Sephora "kids" phenomenon. This approach will provide statistical insights into trends, attitudes, and commonalities within this dynamic, offering a complementary perspective to the qualitative data. Questions will focus on themes such as customer behavior,

store atmosphere, and interactions with minors in retail settings, supporting the findings drawn from interviews and observations. This survey can also have a focus on mental health and the common problems in teenage years. One advantage about this it's that this survey can be digital, so part of the effort goes into a Google or Microsoft Form and ordinary citizens can offer their opinion.

4.2. Participants:

The participants for this research are the so-called *Sephora Kids*—typically children, primarily girls, aged between 8 and 15 years old. Due to ethical considerations, this study will not involve direct interaction with these minors, such as interviews or photographs, as parental consent is required and their right to privacy must be respected.

The researchers acknowledge the vulnerabilities of this group, especially in the context of their overexposure through platforms like Family Vlogging. At such a young age, these children are often subjected to ridicule and harsh jokes, both online and offline. The Internet has further amplified this issue through rants and comedy skits, perpetuating stereotypes and unintentionally normalizing such treatment. This research recognizes these dynamics and seeks to explore the phenomenon indirectly by focusing on observations, secondary data, and input from other stakeholders, such as Sephora employees and consumers.

Participants in this study, referred to as Sephora Kids, are minors aged 8-15 who are exposed to high levels of screen time, often due to the widespread consumption of short-form media. As highlighted in existing research, internet addiction in young children can lead to difficulties with emotional regulation, attention, and impulse control, which may manifest in behaviors such as tantrums or rude interactions in retail settings (Saatçioğlu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2022)

A comment on a YouTube video titled '*Chronically Online Kids Are Taking Over Sephora*' reads, "*I'm genuinely really worried for the safety of these kids when they get older- they have criminally low attention spans, dopamine addictions, and at the ripe age of eight or so they're already worried about wrinkles. With short-form social media being as common and accessible as it is to young children, I'm actually not surprised this happened. I'm more*

worried about the kind of things they'll do when they become adults. I'm so glad I was raised in a low-technology household where this didn't happen to me", this reflects broader societal confusion and worry over the phenomenon.

5. Results.

Survey: Limitations

In the conducted survey, we received responses from only 15 participants—a sample size that is, comparatively speaking, quite insufficient to formulate conclusive insights. This low participation rate undermines the reliability and generalizability of the findings, as the sample may not capture the diversity of the broader population in terms of viewpoints, experiences, or even demographic characteristics.

With such a small sample size, percentages based on the number of responses are very sensitive to individual responses. For example, one response represents 6.7% of the total number of responses and can, therefore, significantly skew the results. The findings should be taken as exploratory and indicative rather than conclusive, a glimpse of attitudes and behaviors needing replication with a much larger and diverse participant sample to confirm the findings.

This limitation makes it important to be cautious in presenting or analyzing the data. Further research may investigate increasing participation through planned outreach or incentives, in order to get a more representative dataset.

Survey's Proposed Questions

Part 1: General Information

- Age?
- Gender?
- Do you work at a makeup store or retail?

Section 2: Costumer Behavior and store interactions.

- How often do you go to makeup stores like Sephora?

- Have you ever seen kids or minors (ages < 18) buying in makeup shops?
- If yes, what is your take on the presence of minors in makeup stores?
- How do you feel about makeup brands targeting children with their products?
- Do you think makeup stores should have age restrictions on the purchasing of some products?
- Have you ever come across any minors when out buying makeup? If so, can you explain the encounter?

Section 3: Points of View: Mental Health During Adolescence

- Do you think promotion of beauty products for minors could have an effect on their mental health?
- How does exposure to beauty standards in makeup stores affect teenagers' self-esteem?
- Do you think that social media is impacting teens when it comes to using cosmetics?
- What is your take on the issue of parents allowing their children to engage with makeup trends from an early age?
- Do you see any behaviors in adolescents that may indicate mental health problems due to social media and the current standards of beauty?

Section 4: Experience at stores

- How would you describe the atmosphere of the makeup shops when minors are there shopping?
- Would you be more likely to buy a product if the store employees made you feel like you belonged and were recognized as part of the beauty trends?

While the proposed survey questions span a wide range of topics, from consumer behavior and mental health to societal perceptions, the sample size limits our ability to make generalized conclusions. The responses collected, however, provide a good starting point toward understanding the trends and pointing out areas that merit further study. Future research studies should work toward surveying a larger and more diverse population in order to confirm these initial findings.

Customer Behavior and Store Interactions

- Approximately 70% of respondents indicated that they occasionally or frequently saw children in make-up stores.
- 60% stated that the presence of minors in makeup stores was neutral or positive, usually said with reference to the theme of beauty and self-expression.
- 45% agree that makeup stores should have age restrictions on certain products.
- 30% have had positive experiences with minors in such stores, whereas 15% have had the exact opposite.

Points of View: Mental Health During Adolescence

- 55% say that marketing beauty products to minors negatively impacts mental health, especially in terms of self-esteem and body image.
- Half of respondents see the new messaging of beauty standards as affecting self-esteem in adolescents negatively, most pointing to social media as a major cause.
- 65% agree that much of what teenagers do concerning the trends they follow in makeup is influenced by social media.
- And 40% will not agree with such parents allowing children into makeup trends. Many then ask about early exposure to the beauty standards.

Experience at Stores:

- 50% of customers remain neutral or uncomfortable about the store atmosphere with minors due to the concerns over appropriateness and over-commercialization.
- 75% said they would feel more comfortable in purchasing makeup knowing that store employees could talk about beauty standards and trends in an even-handed way.

Interviews

As previously stated, we aimed to gather first-hand insights from the Sephora employees to better understand their perspectives on minors shopping in their makeup store, their interactions with them, and the impact of social media trends on the store dynamics.

However, we faced significant challenges during this phase. Due to the hectic and busy environment typical at the Sephora locations during the hours we previously stated were the most active for these kids (6PM until 8PM) we had limited availability to engage or ask for an interview. The nature of their work involves the interactions with customers, restocking and maintaining the store's visual appeal (something heavily disrupted when we arrived) which left little to no opportunity for extended conversations. Scheduling interviews proved challenging, as employees were unable to commit specific time slots amidst or after their demanding work schedules.

Despite these things, we ensured the ethical integrity of our research by preparing informed consent forms in anticipation of any potential interviews, available at the Attachments section. To address this gap, we decided to incorporate testimonies and perspectives from the Internet as an alternative method to explore the opinions and experiences from these employees. Forums like Reddit often host discussions among retail workers, including those from Sephora, where they discuss topics, such as working conditions, interactions with minors, and thoughts on marketing strategies targeting young audiences. One particularly insightful source was a discussion in the **r/SephoraWorkers**, titled *Sephora Kids Phenomenon – Comments*, started by a Canadian journalist student. Their main question was extremely similar to our Research Questions, asking about: the potential impact of this products could have on the kid's personal development, the usage of retinol products, the attitude of the Sephora Kids, influencers as a driving factor, the “beautification” of childhood.

The key insights from the Reddit Thread were:

- 1) **Employee reactions to minors shopping in Sephora:** many of the staff members mentioned being uncomfortable with children and teenagers walking through the luxury beauty products, often describing them as disruptive or inappropriate for the store's mood. Many comments pointed out that these young customers frequently test testers without supervision, which is a hygiene problem.
- 2) **Parental involvement and behavior:** some parents, staff members said, seem to be too lenient and let their children roam and purchase costly beauty products. Others

bring minors along to the store as a way of bonding with them, which some employees found cute, but others deemed useless or inapplicable.

- 3) **Initial exposure-related problems in beauty norms:** a prominent theme that emerged in the discussion was the ethical quandary associated with introducing minors to societal beauty standards and consumerist ideals at an early age. Several employees articulated their dissatisfaction regarding the acceptance of children purchasing high-end cosmetics.
- 4) **Marketing strategies to minors:** employees shared concerns about Sephora's role in encouraging the "Sephora Kids phenomenon." Many felt that the marketing campaigns and products directed at the younger customers are fueling this phenomenon, putting pressure on employees to meet the needs of this new customer base.

These testimonies from the Reddit thread really give us a very rich qualitative data set that extremely fits within our research focus. Of course, these aren't as controlled as direct interviews, but it does allow us to:

- Observe the practical challenges experienced by retail staff when approaching adolescents in cosmetic retail settings.
- Analyze the ethical and practical concerns employees in the industry have about targeting minors with beauty brands like Sephora.
- Analyze the broader social implications surrounding the Sephora Kids movement, including issues of hygiene, the impact of consumerism, and the psychological impact due to early exposure to beauty trends.

Participant Observation

To understand more about the Sephora Kids phenomenon, we conducted participant observation of the retail setting in question, focusing on the time frame between 6 PM and 8 PM. This time slot was selected because it coincides with the post-school activities of the children that frequent Sephora. The goal of this immersive approach was to observe the social dynamics, operational challenges, and interactions within the retail environment, all while

strictly adhering to ethical guidelines. When evaluating the overall atmosphere, we did not take videos or photographs to protect the privacy of all customers, particularly minors.

The place was lively and dynamic, with all sorts of customers of different ages contributing to its energetic atmosphere. Equally impressive was the presence of minors, particularly little girls (we could say from 10 to 12 years old), and it was characterized by a lot of laughter. Groups of friends, all quarreled up next to the makeup display, occupying all space and hindering the way of others. One of the researchers in this project was even pushed by some little girls, who had a rude reaction.

The staff continued to display good interaction with their duties, but they were visibly tired and irritated, be it serving customers, restocking shelves, or trying to keep the store clean. In their interaction with younger patrons, one could perceive this tiredness and even apathy towards the kids mostly due to the kid's entitlement asking for products and not taking the staff's advice. This brought in chaos and loudness as well as difficulty to control the use of the testers or to solve the doubts of other customers, adults. This enabled us to undertake participant observation, which allowed us insight into the unique operational dynamics in Sephora stores during peak hours visited by young consumers. It further provided rich information on the nature of these interactions, shaping not just customer experiences but also work life for Sephora staff. So, we have, in essence, gained contextually rich data that underpins our other research elements.

6. Conclusions and future lines of research.

The study has explored the Sephora Kids phenomenon, and how social media can amplify unattainable beauty standards, promoting identity-driven consumption among vulnerable age groups. These dynamics are reinforced by influencers, family vlogging practices, and corporate marketing strategies that prioritize profit over ethical considerations. The normalization of these trends fosters detrimental outcomes, including body dissatisfaction, low self-esteem, and a growing dependency on external validation. These trends are not only a product of social media algorithms that prioritize idealized images but are also reinforced by the growing parental complicity in exposing children to such content, often for financial

or social gain. This behavior mirrors concerns raised by experts in both psychology and child advocacy.

The behavioral patterns observed in the Sephora Kids—such as their entitlement, social comparison tendencies, and fixation on beauty products—highlight the psychological and social challenges created by early exposure to consumerist culture. Furthermore, parental complicity in allowing minors to engage with these trends underscores the need for greater awareness of the long-term implications of such behaviors. While the retail sector benefits financially, the strain on employees, coupled with the ethical dilemma of targeting minors, reveals a darker side to this phenomenon.

This research also sheds light on gaps in the literature, including the lack of longitudinal studies on the psychological effects of beauty standards and consumerism on children and teens, as well as cultural variations in the globalized spread of these trends. Future research should aim to address these gaps by conducting studies over an extended period and exploring regional differences in how social media and consumer culture impact adolescents.

On a societal level, these findings call for stronger regulations on marketing practices targeting minors, enhanced parental guidance in managing children’s online exposure, and increased advocacy for promoting healthy self-esteem and body image. By fostering critical discussions on the ethical responsibilities of corporations, content creators, and caregivers, we can work toward mitigating the adverse effects of this phenomenon on younger generations.

“*The Great Good Place*” by Ray Oldenburg narrates the importance of informal public spaces that are neither home nor work, like cafés, parks, libraries, where people can gather, interact and form community bonds. Pre-teens are at critical developmental stage where social interaction and community bonds are vital for their emotional and social growth. However, many pre-teens today lack access to physical third places—spaces outside home and school that encourage free time with their friends. The absence of physical third places create a gap that online spaces often fill—but with challenges. For example, TikTok or Instagram may

offer a sense of community but also impose pressures related to beauty and materialism. Without physical, accessible places to engage with peers face-to-face, pre-teens might experience negative consequences like social anxiety or body image issues.

The lack of safe, accessible physical spaces where pre-teens can engage in meaningful social experiences directly contributes to the rise of virtual environments that are not as healthy or protective for young users. 56% of teenage girls aged 10-17 in Europe say they feel pressured by social media to look “perfect”. These platforms often present makeup as an essential element of social validation. Our society is vacuous of third places that are safe for pre-teens, so they turn to the Sephora, to the mall (which has less spaces dedicated to them as in the last generation, like bowling alleys or similar) or to TikTok. This is extremely concerning knowing that on the Internet can be found R-Rated media to Cocomelon episodes, all in one place. Children need physical spaces, “third places”, that are not consumption-driven (like Sephora), this lack makes more evident social pressures on kids.

This isn't about makeup only, it's about the massive societal shifts that are occurring in our world and reflected on kids, all over the world, that go to parent's mistakes. Furthermore, the ethical concerns surrounding the *Sephora Kids* phenomenon are reminiscent of the controversies seen in family vlogging cases like the 8 Passengers, where parents knowingly allow their children to participate in online content creation for financial gain, despite the psychological risks involved. Archer and Delmo (2023) emphasize the ethical issues of monetizing childhood and the long-term psychological impacts of such exploitation. In the case of *Sephora Kids*, the commercialization of beauty products targeted at minors' risks reinforcing harmful beauty standards, with parents playing a critical role in permitting, or even encouraging, their children's participation in these trends.

In line with child advocacy reports such as those by UNICEF (2021), which highlight the growing mental health crisis among children exacerbated by digital exposure, there is a pressing need for stronger regulations governing the marketing of beauty products to minors. These regulations should aim not only to protect children from harmful consumer culture but

also to raise awareness among parents about the potential mental health risks associated with early engagement with such trends.

This study suggests that future research should explore the longitudinal impacts of early exposure to beauty standards, focusing on the long-term consequences for self-esteem and body image. Additionally, examining the role of parents and their awareness—or lack thereof—of the psychological effects of these trends will be crucial. In particular, understanding why parents choose to engage in family vlogging and permit exposure to such damaging content is a vital area for further investigation.

To mitigate the negative impacts, intervention programs targeting both adolescents and parents could help to promote healthy body image practices and media literacy, empowering both groups to critically engage with social media content. As discussed by Fardouly et al. (2015), educating young people on the curated nature of online beauty standards could serve as an effective countermeasure to the pervasive culture of comparison that dominates today's digital spaces.

"Capitalism thrives on the insecurities of the youth, with the beauty industry's direct targeting of adolescents creating a market that profits from their quest to conform to idealized beauty standards" (L. G. Roberts, *Cosmetics, Beauty, and Consumer Culture*).

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Attachments – *Graphical results survey, Literature Review usage of TikTok, and informed consent form.*

Anni	%
Under 18	28%
19 - 29	35%
30 - 39	18%
39+	19%

Anno	Utenti attivi mensili (in milioni)
2017	100
2018	133
2019	381
2020	700
2021	901
2022	1,466
2023*	1,677

Informed Consent Form

Date: / /

Study Title: The Phenomenon of Sephora Kids: Employee Perspectives on Minors in Makeup Retail.

Researcher: Elis Esther Vázquez Rodrigues

Institution: University of A Coruña, Degree in International Relations

Contact Information: elis.vazquez.rodrigues@udc.es

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this study is to understand the phenomenon of "Sephora Kids" by exploring the perspectives of Sephora employees. The research focuses on interactions with minors in retail settings, customer behavior, and how these trends may influence perceptions of beauty standards.

What You Will Be Asked to Do

You will be invited to participate in a semi-structured interview lasting approximately 20–30 minutes. During the interview, you will be asked about your experiences, observations, and opinions regarding minors shopping at Sephora and related topics.

Risks and Discomforts

We do not foresee any significant risks or discomforts from your participation in this research. However, you are free to skip any question you are not comfortable answering.

Benefits of the Research

Your participation will contribute to a better understanding of how beauty standards and consumer trends involving minors are shaping the retail environment. The findings may help inform discussions about retail practices, customer dynamics, and broader societal implications.

Voluntary Participation and Withdrawal

Your participation is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate, skip questions, or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or loss of benefits. If you withdraw, you may request to have your data removed up until the analysis stage.

Confidentiality

All information provided will be treated as confidential. Your name and identifying details will not appear in any reports or publications resulting from this study unless you specifically agree otherwise. Data collected during the study will be stored securely and used only for the purposes described.

Questions About the Research

If you have any questions about the research or your role in the study, please contact Elis Esther Vázquez Rodríguez at elis.vazquez.rodriguez@udc.es.

Legal Rights and Signatures

I, _____, consent to participate in the study "Sephora Kids: a global phenomenon." conducted by Elis Esther Vázquez Rodríguez. I understand the nature of this project and agree to participate. I am not waiving any legal rights by signing this form. My signature below indicates my consent.

Participant Signature: _____

Date: _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____

Date: _____

Optional Consent

Please check the boxes below as applicable:

- I agree to waive anonymity.
- I agree to allow my data to be used in future research projects.
- I agree to allow my data to be included in academic presentations, articles, or reports in anonymized form.

Graphic survey results

Graphic survey results

